

This document is provided as technical supplementary material accompanying the primary research publication. It has not undergone the formal peer review process. The purpose of this release is to share preliminary findings and present the technical methodologies employed in our research. Readers are encouraged to consider this context when evaluating the content.

Supplementary material (C) for: A metric approach to paradigmatic collaboration: case study with Prolog

Mikel Vandeloise

University of Namur, Belgium

Namur Digital Institute

(e-mail: mikel.vandeloise@student.unamur.be)

submitted 26/04/2024; revised 26/04/2024; accepted 26/04/2024

Abstract

This supplementary material utilizes the metric approach established in our previous work to analyse the collaboration potential of multi-paradigm programming languages, specifically focusing on Curry and AKL. By applying the developed metrics to these languages, we assess their ability to integrate with various programming paradigms, highlighting the challenges and opportunities inherent in multi-paradigm environments. The results underscore the complexities of paradigmatic interactions and provide a nuanced understanding of how different programming paradigms can effectively collaborate within software development.

KEYWORDS: Multi-paradigm Programming Languages, Curry, AKL, Programming Paradigms, Paradigmatic Collaboration, Metric Analysis

1 Introduction

This additional material builds on the foundational work documented in our main study (Vandeloise et al. 2024), where a comprehensive taxonomy of programming paradigms and their interactions was introduced. In this extension, we focus on the practical application of the metrics developed to assess the potential for collaboration between different programming paradigms and languages.

Data were generated using a Haskell model of the various metrics, with the source code available on (Vandeloise 2024a). Datasets are available on (Vandeloise 2024b) in both "Cleaned" and "Raw" formats for paradigms and languages, supporting various analyses and further uses:

- `CollaborationMetric_Languages_Cleaned.csv`
- `CollaborationMetric_Languages_Raw.csv`
- `CollaborationMetric_Paradigms_Cleaned.csv`
- `CollaborationMetric_Paradigms_Raw.csv`

The following sections of this paper detail the methodological approaches used to identify collaboration thresholds and specific results related to various programming paradigms and languages, including Curry and AKL. With this additional material, we provide a robust methodological framework that contributes significantly to the understanding of how different programming paradigms can effectively collaborate.

2 analysis of Curry, a multi-paradigm language

Language	P
Curry	{lazy concurrent constraint programming, lazy declarative concurrent programming, nonmonotonic dataflow programming}
lazy concurrent constraint programming	$\left(\begin{array}{l} \{\text{record, procedure, closure, unification, search, solver, thread, by-need sync}\}, \\ \{\text{concurrent constraint programming}\}, \\ \{\}, \\ \text{True}, \\ \text{False}, \\ \text{logic and constraint} \end{array} \right)$
lazy declarative concurrent programming	$\left(\begin{array}{l} \{\text{record, procedure, closure, thread, single assign, by-need sync}\}, \\ \{\text{lazy functional programming, declarative concurrent programming}\}, \\ \{\}, \\ \text{True}, \\ \text{False}, \\ \text{functional} \end{array} \right)$
nonmonotonic dataflow programming	$\left(\begin{array}{l} \{\text{record, procedure, closure, thread, single assign, nondet choice}\}, \\ \{\text{declarative concurrent programming}\}, \\ \{\text{continuous synchronous programming}\}, \\ \text{True}, \\ \text{True}, \\ \text{reactive} \end{array} \right)$

MC for lazy concurrent constraint programming

MC for lazy declarative concurrent programming

The quantitative analysis of the lazy concurrent constraint programming and lazy concurrent declarative programming paradigms shows a moderate to low potential for collaboration with the majority of the paradigms analysed, with most scores not exceeding

S-M(C) for: A metric approach to paradigmatic collaboration: case study with Prolog3

the 50% threshold. However, a significant increase in collaboration potential is observed within the "logic and constraint" meta-paradigms for the former and with the functional paradigms for the latter, indicating an increased ability to generate synergies within these specific groups. Nevertheless, a decrease in collaboration is noted with the deterministic logic and relational logic paradigms for lazy concurrent constraint programming, despite a common membership of the "logic and constraint" meta-paradigm. This observation suggests that factors inherent in individual paradigms may influence the potential for collaboration. These results highlight the importance of considering unique attributes and meta-paradigmatic memberships when assessing the potential for collaboration between programming paradigms. They also reveal the complexity of paradigmatic interactions, illustrating the diversity and heterogeneity of collaboration potentials.

An analysis of the collaboration potential of the nonmonotonic dataflow paradigm reveals mostly weak indices, with the majority not reaching the 25% threshold. However, collaboration peaks with 'synchronous continuous programming', a predictable convergence as the latter extends the nonmonotonic dataflow paradigm with synchronisation on partial termination. There is also notable synergy with 'discrete synchronous programming', highlighting an inherent compatibility within the "reactive" meta-paradigm. The ability to integrate nonmonotonic data flow is therefore influenced by conceptual affinities and membership of a common meta-paradigm.

Analysis of Curry's collaboration data reveals a moderate to low spectrum, with a maximum of 50%. This profile is similar to that of other languages in the "logic and constraint" meta-paradigm. However, the multi-paradigm nature of Curry and the integration challenges it entails result in particularly low collaboration scores. Interestingly, higher collaboration is observed with Scheme and ML (functional paradigm), suggesting moderate compatibility. These points of convergence could facilitate integration into functional programming environments. Remarkably, Curry shows its strongest collaboration with FCP, sharing the nonmonotonic dataflow paradigm. This shared paradigm suggests a potentially important area of synergy for further exploration. In conclusion, the analysis highlights the importance of developing integration strategies that consider Curry's unique ability to adapt to various paradigms, thereby maximising its strengths in multi-paradigm contexts.

3 analysis of AKL, a multi-paradigm language

Language	P
AKL	{concurrent constraint programming, nonmonotonic dataflow programming, multi-agent dataflow programming, multi-agent programming}

$$\text{concurrent constraint programming} = \left(\begin{array}{l} \{\text{record, procedure, closure, unification, search, solver, thread}\}, \\ \{\text{constraint logic programming}\}, \\ \{\text{lazy concurrent constraint programming}\}, \\ \text{True}, \\ \text{False}, \\ \text{logic and constraint} \end{array} \right)$$

$$\text{nonmonotonic dataflow programming} = \left(\begin{array}{l} \{\text{record, procedure, closure, thread, single assign, nondet choice}\}, \\ \{\text{declarative concurrent programming}\}, \\ \{\text{continuous synchronous programming}\}, \\ \text{True}, \\ \text{True}, \\ \text{reactive} \end{array} \right)$$

$$\text{multi agent dataflow programming} = \left(\begin{array}{l} \{\text{record, procedure, closure, thread, single assign, channel}\}, \\ \{\text{declarative concurrent programming}\}, \\ \{\}, \\ \text{True}, \\ \text{True}, \\ \text{dataflow and message passing} \end{array} \right)$$

$$\text{multi agent programming} = \left(\begin{array}{l} \{\text{record, procedure, closure, channel, thread}\}, \\ \{\text{event loop programming}\}, \\ \{\text{active object programming}\}, \\ \text{True}, \\ \text{True}, \\ \text{message passing} \end{array} \right)$$

The concurrent constraint programming paradigm has been analysed in (Vandeloise et al. 2024), and the nonmonotonic dataflow programming paradigm has been similarly evaluated, as detailed earlier in this document.

Analysis of the graph indicates that interactions between most of the paradigms generate an MC of less than 25%, suggesting a limited capacity for collaboration in the context of the multi-agent dataflow paradigm. Superior performance is observed within the paradigms associated with the "dataflow and message passing" and "message passing" meta-paradigms, revealing higher MC scores. These results indicate greater compatibility within these specific meta-paradigms.

S-M(C) for: A metric approach to paradigmatic collaboration: case study with Prolog5

Examination of the MC for multi-agent programming graph reveals that the MC levels associated with the majority of paradigms are below 25%, indicating a limited capacity for inter-paradigmatic collaboration. However, the 'active object programming' and 'event loop programming' paradigms show significantly higher MC, revealing superior inter-paradigmatic synergy. These results corroborate the hypothesis that belonging to a common meta-paradigm improves the possibilities for cross-paradigm collaboration.

Analysis of AKL's data reveals a moderate to low spectrum of potential collaboration, with a maximum of 50%. This profile is similar to that of other languages in the "logic and constraint" meta-paradigm, specially Curry. However, the multi-paradigm nature of AKL and the integration challenges it entails result in particularly low collaboration scores. Remarkably, AKL shows its strongest collaboration with FCP, sharing the nonmonotonic data flow paradigm, and Erlang, sharing the multi-agent programming paradigm. These shared paradigms suggest potentially important areas of synergy to be explored further. In conclusion, the analysis highlights the importance of developing integration strategies that consider AKL's unique ability to adapt to different paradigms, thereby maximising its strengths in multi-paradigm contexts.

4 Conclusion

In summary, this study has deepened the understanding of the interactions between different programming paradigms using dedicated metrics to assess the potential for collaboration. Our analyses have highlighted that, although some paradigm combinations offer moderate to low potential for synergy, there are specific cases where increased collaboration is possible, especially within meta-paradigms.

The case of multi-paradigm languages such as Curry and AKL illustrates the challenges of integration particularly well. These languages generally display moderate to

low collaboration scores, but show affinities in specific contexts that could be exploited to improve cross-paradigm integration. These observations highlight the importance of adopting adaptive integration strategies that maximise the unique strengths of multi-paradigm languages in heterogeneous programming environments.

Thus, this research contributes to a more in-depth understanding of the complex dynamics of collaboration between programming paradigms and lays the groundwork for future studies that could explore more sophisticated integration strategies. It is imperative to continue developing tools and methodologies that facilitate the productive cohabitation of diverse paradigms in software development, a growing necessity in today's technological landscape.

References

- VANDELOISE, M. 2024a. Metrics of collaboration across programming paradigms and languages: Code. GitHub. <https://github.com/Vdloisem/MCC>.
- VANDELOISE, M. 2024b. Metrics of collaboration across programming paradigms and languages: Comprehensive dataset. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11077187>.
- VANDELOISE, M., YERNAUX, G., AND VANHOOF, W. 2024. A metric approach to paradigmatic collaboration: case study with prolog. Tech. rep., University of Namur, Namur Digital Institute, Namur, Belgium.